

Framework For Mitigating the Risks of Synthetic Media and Misinformation in Nigerian Political Communication

Titi Fola-Adebayo¹, Babatunde Raphael Ojebuyi², Tayo Raymond Eegunlusi³, Olayinka A. Egbokhare⁴, Oluwayemisi Olusola Adebomi⁵, Oluchi Ojinamma Okere⁶, Funmilayo Mabel Oguntade⁷, Peter Adebayo Aborisade⁸, Funmilayo Omolabake Olubode-Sawe⁹, Akindeji Ibrahim Makinde¹⁰, Adamkolo Mohammed Ibrahim¹¹, Abimbola O. Ogunduyile¹², Mayokun Joyce Olowoniyi¹³

^{1,3,5,7,8,9,12,13} General Studies Unit, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria.

^{2,4} Department of Communication and Language Arts, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

⁶ Department of Education Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria.

¹¹ Department of Mass Communication, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Nigeria.

¹⁰ Department of Information Systems, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria.

¹Corresponding Author's Email: tjfoladebayo@futa.edu.ng

Received: 15/09/2025; *Accepted:* 06/12/2025; *Published:* 18/02/2026

Abstract: Deepfakes, synthetic media, and other manipulated media generated through artificial intelligence and used with malicious intent have the potential to threaten national unity by causing social unrest and eroding trust, particularly during elections. The evolution of synthetic media in political communication worsens misinformation by increasing voter manipulation and bias. The trend of using manipulated information during the campaign season in Nigeria demands attention, especially in respect to mitigation techniques. This study, thus, proposes a framework for mitigating risks associated with synthetic media and misinformation in Nigerian political communication using a qualitative systematic review design. A systematic synthesis of existing literature on fake news mitigation strategies, within the context of synthetic media (deepfakes) indicates that a multi-dimensional socio-technical framework is the best roadmap for policymakers, election managers, tech companies, and civil society to safeguard Nigeria's democratic processes from the threat of manipulated media.

Keywords: Deepfakes; Synthetic media; Fake News; Political Communication; Socio-Technical Framework

INTRODUCTION

Fake news and misinformation threaten Nigeria's information integrity, unity, and democratic processes, particularly within political communication (Salihu, 2020). The rise of social media has transformed how information is shared, especially with the evolution of social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp as primary channels for the rapid spread of false content (Igben & Acchugbue, 2024). Factors like the pursuit of media relevance, government manipulation, profit motives and inadequate internet regulation continue to contribute to its prevalence (Owojecho, 2021). The impact of this phenomenon is quite severe and can influence election outcomes (Abiodun, 2024), and affect the integrity of civic engagement, thereby posing a risk to the national political stability.

Measures like strengthened regulatory frameworks and legislative approaches are commonly cited as solutions to curb the dissemination of false information (Abiodun, 2024; Shuni & Mukoshy, 2024). Widespread media literacy programmes to empower citizens to identify and reject fake news (Abiodun, 2024) have also been proffered as a way out. However, technological solutions like the promotion of greater transparency in social media algorithms and supporting collaboration between digital platforms and fact-checking organisations (Shuni & Mukoshy, 2024)

might be more effective as they are both preventative and recovery approaches that can help mitigate the risks associated with computational propaganda (Robertson & Meintjes, 2021).

Fake news through synthetic media and deepfakes are a novel threat, because of their high level of realism and the increasing difficulty of detection. It is becoming difficult to distinguish between genuine facial images and video clips from manipulated given the rapid progress in deep learning technologies. The realism and convincing quality of such media strongly influence users' perception, trust and overall interaction with the technology (Matli, 2024).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Synthetic media includes content that is generated through algorithms or digital manipulation of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning techniques. This category of media includes deepfake videos, voice cloning, AI-generated images and fabricated textual contents which have the capacity to create highly realistic impersonations of individuals, and images that could complicate efforts to discern authentic political messages from fabricated ones.

Synthetic media can be weaponised to erode public trust and destabilise political institutions. Ekpang et al. (2023) observed that deepfakes were deployed as a tool to attack, and used to smear political candidates and mislead voters, during the last election. A widely circulated audio clip alleged to feature the Labour Party presidential candidate Peter Obi and Pastor David Oyedepo, went viral by attracting over 10 million listens on X (formerly Twitter). Though publicly denied by the candidate, the clip was suspected to be a deepfake due to its ambiguous provenance. Deepfake narratives have also targeted former President Muhammadu Buhari, reviving conspiracy theories about a supposed body double from Sudan (BBC News Pidgin, 2018).

The structure and dynamics of social media platforms are exploited by synthetic media to achieve rapid and widespread dissemination through videos that mimic public figures, voice cloning that imitates political actors, misleading narratives and fabricated documents or chat transcripts presented as authentic evidence. Platforms like WhatsApp, with its extensive user base in Nigeria, end-to-end encryption, and broadcast features, enable the swift circulation of unverified content. X (formerly Twitter) amplifies such material through real-time interactions and algorithm-driven visibility, while Facebook and Instagram facilitate the spread of targeted political advertisements and misinformation propagated through influencers.

INFLUENCER NETWORKS AND COORDINATED AMPLIFICATION

The integration of synthetic media into Nigeria's political ecosystem has transformed the nature of political communication. AI-generated content such as deepfakes and voice clones has introduced a new layer of complexity, where perception increasingly overrides authenticity. Political campaigns now employ influencers and coordinated digital operatives to circulate synthetic media to shape narratives and manipulate public sentiment. Uwalaka et al. (2025) document the activities of groups known as the "Data Boys". These are covert online actors funded by political campaigns to aggressively disseminate tailored messages such as exaggerated achievements and fabricated corruption scandals. During the 2023 general elections, viral deepfake videos and AI-generated endorsements were used to launder the images or discredit candidates. These contents effectively bypassed traditional media gatekeeping (Davis, 2024;

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

Ekpang et al., 2023), and exploited confirmation bias to make false content more believable to partisan audiences.

While some digital influencers engage in civic education and legitimate advocacy, others deliberately contribute to information disorder by disseminating disinformation with strategic precision. In the past, political discourse relied on verifiable statements, public appearances and journalistic scrutiny; however, with the rise of synthetic media, the boundaries have become blurred. The convergence of paid promotion, partisan loyalty, and algorithmic impacts present major challenges for regulatory bodies and democratic institutions. Deepfakes and manipulated materials evoke strong emotional reactions and may reinforce existing biases, thereby influencing voter behaviour. In a Q&A with Hannah Ajakaiye, Davis (2024) observed that deepfakes targeting candidates such as Peter Obi and Atiku Abubakar circulated widely on platforms like WhatsApp and X (formerly Twitter) and attracted millions of views. These convincing media artefacts were difficult to debunk in real time and created widespread misinformation and voter confusion.

The political landscape of Nigeria with its deep ethnic and religious identities has made it vulnerable to the weaponisation of synthetic media. Deepfakes have been deployed to exploit societal divisions by depicting candidates in ways that provoke tribal or sectarian hostility. For instance, fabricated videos falsely showing candidates making inflammatory remarks against specific ethnic or religious groups spread rapidly during the 2023 elections (Centre for Democracy and Development, 2023). Such contents heightened tensions in politically volatile regions, and were noted to lead to incidents of unrest and voter intimidation. The emotional realism of deepfakes makes them especially dangerous in fragile democracies like Nigeria.

The proliferation of synthetic media has also undermined the credibility of traditional journalism. Journalists now face growing pressure to verify manipulated multimedia content in real time, often without access to advanced detection technologies. Oyedeji (2024) highlights the difficulties Nigerian fact-checkers faced during the 2023 elections, noting that verification platforms such as “Dubawa” and “FactCheckHub” struggled to keep pace with the sheer volume and virality of synthetic disinformation. Due to this, public trust in mainstream media declined sharply. Olley & Elope (2024) found that only 59.65% of surveyed Nigerians expressed confidence in traditional media’s political reporting, with many perceiving journalists as possibly complicit in spreading false narratives.

Beyond electoral outcomes, the rise of synthetic media carries serious psychological and social consequences. Furizal et al. (2025) warn that journalists and public figures targeted by deepfakes often experience reputational damage and mental distress. These personal attacks which frequently involve fabricated scandals or inflammatory statements could lead to social ostracism, professional setbacks, and withdrawal from public engagements. Similarly, research by Constantineanu (2024) states that deepfakes contribute to growing social fragmentation by eroding the ability of citizens to distinguish truth from falsehood.

SYNTHETIC MEDIA AND FAKE NEWS MITIGATION STRATEGIES

A number of studies show that human aptitude for detecting synthetic media is limited. The current quality of deepfakes exploit human cognitive and psychological processes as shown in a quasi-experimental study by Sanchez-Acedo et al. (2024) which investigated the effectiveness of traditional media and information literacy in the age of hyper-realistic deepfakes. The research, conducted with 80 young people, reveals high vulnerability in how audiences assess information. The study shows that the high level of realism of AI-generated images consistently overrode contextual cues, such as the reputation of the media source, as participants failed to perform a critical reading of the context of the information.

Similarly, human detection is challenging and lacks a singular, reliable method. In Neo et al.'s (2025) study, participants could generally distinguish between authentic and deepfake videos and were significantly better at identifying real contents. Their detection strategies were focused most on the subject's features, such as facial characteristics and behaviour, while largely ignoring general production quality cues. This over-reliance on visual traits presents a growing danger, as the rapid advancement of deepfake technology makes these very features easier to manipulate in a convincing manner.

Ahmed et al. (2024) reveal that the Illusion of Truth Effect, where repeated exposure increases perceived accuracy applies to deepfakes across different sociopolitical settings and genres. This effect was more prevalent among participants who consume news on social media. This proves that fake news consumption vulnerability could override cognitive ability, as repetition and media habits amplified believability.

Mai et al. (2023) researched human vulnerability in detecting speech deepfakes. Their study, involving 529 individuals listening to English and Mandarin audio, found that listeners could only correctly identify deepfakes 73% of the time, demonstrating that human detection capability is unreliable and only slightly improves with increased awareness (e.g., providing examples of deepfakes). There was no significant difference in detection performance between English and Mandarin speakers, suggesting a universal challenge. The authors also note that even in a controlled environment where participants were explicitly aware of the presence of deepfakes and the deepfakes were not created using the absolute state-of-the-art technology, detection rates were still low.

A systematic review of 40 studies found that human deepfake detection accuracy varies generally and is very much influenced by both person-level (e.g., cognitive ability) and stimuli-level (e.g., deepfake quality) factors, with some results showing humans outperforming AI and others not. The findings, derived from a search of five databases up to December 2023, suggest the potential for human-AI collaboration since both focus on different detection aspects (Somoray et al., 2025).

Several deepfake detection models commonly appear across recent literature, demonstrating both strengths and limitations in performance and generalisability. For instance, the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), particularly architectures like VGG16, ResNet-50, Xception, and

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

EfficientNet is the most widely used of these models due to its effectiveness in extracting spatial features from images and video frames (Heidari et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2025). Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are frequently combined with CNNs to capture temporal inconsistencies in video sequences, enhancing detection by modelling frame-level dynamics (Ramanaharan et al., 2025).

Vision Transformers (ViT) and hybrid models like CNN-ViT are gaining prominence for their ability to capture global contextual information and long-range dependencies, outperforming CNNs in cross-dataset evaluations (Wodajo & Atnafu, 2021). In a systematic review carried out by Ramanaharan et al. (2025) report that hybrid and multimodal architectures specifically those combining Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for spatial analysis with Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) or Vision Transformers (ViTs) for temporal consistency provide the most effective defence. Meanwhile, current models struggle significantly to generalise across unseen manipulation types due to dataset overfitting. In other words, the various computational models have their areas of applicability and strength.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative, systematic approach to review and synthesize the literature on fake news mitigation, specifically within the context of synthetic media (deepfakes). The primary objective of the study is to construct a conceptual framework that addresses means for mitigating the risks associated with deepfakes. Literature searched for this systematic review transcends disciplinary boundaries, drawing from media studies, communication, information science, computer ethics and cybersecurity.

Peer-reviewed articles published between 2018 and 2025 in multidisciplinary databases (including Academic Search Premier and Communication & Mass Media Complete) of the EBSCO collection were searched to identify full-text articles that specifically address “synthetic media” or “deepfakes” in conjunction with detection and mitigation strategies.

The selection process was guided by strict thematic relevance. Articles were retained only if (i) they proposed, evaluated, or discussed tangible mitigation strategies, whether technical, legal, or social; and (ii) were published in English. Editorials, opinion pieces, and sources lacking sufficient conceptual depth were omitted to ensure analytical rigour. Following a comprehensive screening process involving title and abstract review to ensure thematic fit, a final corpus of 93 articles was selected for in-depth analysis.

Due to the increase in the trend of manipulated information in Nigeria, especially during electioneering, and their accompanying consequences, this study proposes a framework for mitigating risks associated with synthetic media and misinformation in Nigerian political communication. The paper contributes to the discourse on disinformation by using a qualitative systematic review design to synthesise existing literature on fake news mitigation strategies within the context of synthetic media. The findings of the review formed the basis for the framework.

RESULTS

A detailed review of the articles showed that 93 articles fit the criteria.

Table 1: Selected articles

Strategy	Article Count	Percentage
Technological and Algorithmic-Based Strategies	65	70%
Legal and Regulatory Measures	16	17%
Human-Centred Strategies	12	13%
Total	93	100%

Table 1 presents the information. These articles were classified into three major strategies: technological detection and algorithmic-based strategies, legal and regulatory measures and human-centred Strategies. While most of the articles (70%) were technological in content and context, 17% of the articles were based on legal and regulatory strategies and 13% were based on human-centric strategies.

Table 2: Identified Strategies

Technological & Algorithmic based strategies	Legal & Regulatory Strategies	Human-Centred Approaches
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proactive watermarking ● Deepfake detection tools based on various competing models ● Interactive web platforms (AI-driven detection training) ● Automated AI disclaimers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Criminal penalties for malicious use ● Whistleblower incentives ● Global agreements / International cooperation ● Establish a National Synthetic Media Oversight Body ● Mandatory labelling laws ● Strict liability for malicious tools ● Regulation of AI platforms ● Enforcement of Ethical AI guidelines for political campaigns ● Regular policy reviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Media literacy ● Public awareness campaigns ● Fact-checking partnerships ● Public correction notices ● National digital literacy curriculum ● Interactive web platforms (educational games)

Table 2 is a presentation of specific mitigation strategies recommended or applied by the articles, under the following themes: technological, legal and regulatory and human centred strategies. Legal and regulatory and human-centred strategies seem to be more varied than the technological tools. The result also shows the variety of solutions that exist for mitigating the risks of fake news.

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

Table 3: A staged categorisation of intervention strategies

Preventive & Proactive	Detective Strategies	Corrective Strategies	Resilience Building
→	→	→	
Proactive watermarking	Deepfake detection tools based on various competing models	Public correction notices	Media literacy
AI Disclaimers		Fact-checking partnerships	Public awareness campaigns
Mandatory labelling laws	Interactive web platforms (detection training)	Criminal penalties for malicious use	National digital literacy curriculum
Ethical AI guidelines for political campaigns	Improve critical thinking skills		Interactive web platforms (educational games)
Regulation of AI platforms			
Strict liability for malicious tools			
Establish a National Synthetic Media Oversight Body			
Global agreements / International cooperation			
Whistleblower Incentives			

Table 3 shows a continuum of strategies starting from preventive and reactive means to corrective strategies. Proactive strategies (are actions taken in advance to deter or reduce the creation and spread of harmful synthetic media, they stop deepfakes at the source; detective strategies are systems that identify synthetic or manipulated media); Corrective measures are actions taken after harmful content has been identified, to mitigate its impact, they are reactive in nature. Resilience building are long-term efforts designed to strengthen societal, individual, and institutional capacity to resist manipulation, irrespective of detection or correction.

FINDINGS

The thematic analysis identified three overarching categories of mitigation strategies:

- i. Technological strategies that deploy machine learning and deep learning models
- ii. Legal, Regulatory and governance frameworks; and
- iii. Social and Human centred strategies

Technological and Algorithmic-Based Strategies

Technological mitigation strategies in the literature generally fall into two categories: reactive detection (identifying fakes after they spread) and proactive prevention (marking contents at the source).

Within the reactive methods, the dominant trend involves deploying increasingly sophisticated AI to distinguish authentic media from forgeries. The literature indicates a distinct shift away from simple models toward “hybrid” architectures. Rather than isolating a single type of flaw, these advanced systems leverage complementary analytical strengths: they scrutinise minute surface details, such as textures, while simultaneously analysing the broader structural integrity of the image or video (Kaddar et al., 2024; Deressa et al., 2025; Fang et al., 2025).

Researchers have thus sought to interrogate the digital “DNA” of a file by analysing invisible frequency data, flagging inconsistencies in facial geometry, or treating deepfakes as temporal anomalies (Rosca & Stancu, 2025; Yao et al., 2025). However, despite offering improved accuracy, these hybrid models are hampered by the “generalisation problem”: a system trained to spot one specific manipulation technique often fails to recognise newer, unseen variations (Zhang et al., 2025). Furthermore, the immense computing power required for these tools restricts their real-time application, prompting a recent push for “lightweight” models that are more accessible for everyday deployment (Al Redhaei et al., 2025; Zeeshan, 2025).

Liu et al. (2025) address the limits of purely digital detection by highlighting the potentials of biological markers. They argue that as synthetic media become visually perfect, detection must focus on biological impossibilities rather than digital glitches. Their work demonstrates that deepfakes often fail to perfectly synchronise eye and mouth movements. Detecting these subtle disruptions in human physiology has proven robust even against advanced forgeries.

Finally, the literature suggests a structural pivot toward proactive measures. Nadimpalli & Rattani (2024) propose embedding visible watermarks into the generation process itself. Unlike forensic tools that analyse content *ex post facto*, this approach aims to make the artificial nature of the content immediately obvious to both human eyes and automated scanners, effectively “tagging” disinformation before it can circulate.

Legal and Regulatory

Legal and regulatory strategies focus on creating rules, responsibilities, and consequences to deter the malicious creation and distribution of misinformation. It establishes a framework for accountability, and it is driven by deterrents, oversight, transparency and cooperation. Ranieri (2025) suggested a solution such as federal legislation requiring creators to conspicuously label their content as “altered”. This disclosure-based strategy focuses on transparency and empowering the public to distinguish between authentic and manipulated media, rather than banning the technology or penalising its creators. Another regulatory framework by Sherman (2025) concentrates on the use of deepfakes for financial crimes. The proposed solution is a multi-pronged strategy aimed at deterring and punishing the end-user, which includes creating sentencing enhancements, offering whistleblower incentives, and establishing an international agreement to standardise these measures. This approach is punitive and focuses on strengthening criminal law to prosecute those who use deepfakes for financial fraud.

Human-Centred Strategies

Human-centred strategies focus on empowering individuals and society to critically assess information, reducing the impact of misinformation when it inevitably gets through technological

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

and legal filters. They are mostly implemented through Education (Media literacy and a National digital literacy curriculum) and public Engagement (Public awareness campaigns and fact-checking).

The most direct strategy for mitigating deepfake deception is the use of disclaimers and disclosures. Research shows that explicitly labelling content as AI-generated can be effective, though its impact is relative. In the context of political parodies, an AI disclaimer significantly improves the audience's ability to recognise the content as satire, which in turn influences how they engage with the message (Lu & Yuan, 2024). Extended disclosures that explain the consequences of the manipulation are more successful in reducing the content's perceived factuality (Karpinska-Krakiwiak & Eisend, 2025). This distinction between realism and factuality is crucial, as it suggests that even when viewers know something is fake, the realistic portrayal can still leave a powerful impression.

Education and media literacy, particularly for younger audiences who are digital natives is another human-centred strategy for mitigating deepfake deception. Studies show that the exceptional verisimilitude of deepfakes often causes viewers to prioritise the visual image over contextual clues, such as the reputation of the media source, making traditional media literacy approaches less effective (Sanchez-Acedo et al., 2024). This calls for a reorientation of media literacy education. A promising approach is experiential learning, where youth actively engage in the process of creating deepfakes. A study by Naffi et al. (2025) found that this hands-on experience, informed by personal construct theory, empowered participants by helping them understand their own vulnerabilities to manipulation. This process transforms them from passive consumers into empowered digital citizens motivated to critically assess online information, suggesting that deep, reflective learning is essential to building societal resilience.

Malinka et al. (2024) recommend other strategies to enhance this skill for individuals to discern deepfakes. He pointed at the requirement to shift from passive consumption to active analysis and verification. Suggestions include raising public awareness through exposure to deepfake examples and specific training to identify audio-visual artifacts and training the public in verification and caution, advocating for the adoption of methods like SIFT (Stop, Investigate, Find and Trace), also encouraging a general mindset of scepticism towards online information. Malinka et al (2024) propose the creation of a comprehensive educational platform web application that would offer interactive training and tutorials on detection tools to build public resilience against manipulation. Other methods suggested by the literature on strategies of mitigating the effects of deepfake and synthetic media are fact-checking, source verification and verification mechanisms, media and information literacy education focused on critical consumption, digital ethics and cognitive resilience.

Framework Development

Findings from the thematic synthesis which identified the categories of strategies informed the construction of a conceptual framework for fake news mitigation of deepfakes and synthetic media ecosystems. The framework integrates technological, social, and institutional (legal and regulatory) strategies which cut across preventive, detection, and corrective measures. This

process produced a holistic model that situates mitigation strategies along a continuum – from proactive prevention and real-time detection to post-event correction and resilience-building.

Figure 1. A Socio-Technical Framework for Deepfake Mitigation in Nigerian Political Communication (Illustration generated using Google Gemini) Source: Author’s elaboration based on the reviewed literature.

DISCUSSION

The pervasive threat of deepfakes in Nigeria’s political communication demands a multi-tiered mitigation strategy, harmonising technological, legal/regulatory, and human-centred interventions across four critical stages - the preventive and proactive measures, detective, corrective and resilience building. While identifying the strategies as important, more focus should be placed on how and when they can be applied.

Preventive and proactive measures such as AI disclaimers, proactive watermarking, mandatory labelling laws, and regulation of AI platforms, aim to stop synthetic media from being misused before it spreads. Technological solutions like proactive watermarking (embedding digital signatures in authentic content) and legal tools such as mandatory labelling laws and strict liability for malicious tools can pre-emptively curb synthetic media at its source. For Nigeria, enacting ethical guidelines for political campaigns and regulating AI platforms (e.g., requiring NCC-licensed tools to integrate safeguards) would deter malicious actors. Human-centred tactics, like whistleblower incentives, could make good use of Nigeria’s community-based vigilance networks to report violations early.

Detection strategies, though mostly reactive and generally technological by design, remain indispensable in the technological era. AI-powered forensic tools must be tailored to Nigeria’s low-bandwidth environments (e.g., lightweight ResNet models for mobile access), while

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

interactive web platforms could train INEC staff and journalists to spot deepfakes. Legal frameworks supporting national oversight bodies would centralize detection efforts, ensuring rapid cross-agency coordination during elections.

Corrective Measures are most useful after deepfakes have been exposed. Legal actions (criminal penalties, election tribunals) and human-centred fact-checking partnerships (e.g., Dubawa or Africa Check collaborating with broadcasters) must deploy public correction notices across radio, SMS, and social media. The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) could mandate retractions to counter viral disinformation.

Finally, resilience-building is long-term and generally relies on human-centred media literacy and national digital curricula integrated into civic education. Technological interactive games (e.g., Yoruba/Hausa-language deepfake simulations) are useful tools to build grassroots vigilance.

The mitigation of deepfakes, particularly in the context of political misinformation, requires a multi-pronged and integrative approaches that integrate technological, human-centred, and legal/regulatory strategies across different stages of the deepfake lifecycle. A staged, multi-pronged approach is non-negotiable for safeguarding Nigeria's electoral integrity against synthetic media's evolving sophistication.

No single intervention is sufficient on its own; success lies in the coordination of these layered strategies across time and domains. For instance, while detection tools may identify a fake video, their impact is amplified when paired with rapid corrective fact-checking and public alerts. Similarly, legal deterrents gain strength when supported by resilient, media-literate citizens who reject manipulated contents. A comprehensive defense that takes cognizance of the right strategies at the appropriate stage, and which synthesizes both human-centered and technological approaches, must be adopted for successful risk mitigation.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A seamless integration of preventive, detective and corrective measures that include technological solutions based on deep learning and AI-based methods, legal and regulatory measures, and resilience building (human-centred) strategies should be used to manage high levels of political dissemination associated with Nigerian political processes. In the long run, the most sustainable defence for Nigeria's democracy lies in cultivating societal resilience, because technological and legal filters remain imperfect. Long-term stability requires a strategic shift toward empowering the electorate through comprehensive media and digital literacy integrated directly into the national curriculum. Citizens should be adequately equipped with critical skills to verify sources and identify digital propaganda. Such training encourages a culture of 'scepticism-by-design,' which is necessary to maintain information integrity within Nigeria's highly complex and technologically-mediated political landscape. Media organisations and civil society also need to form sustainable partnerships for rapid fact-checking. A socio-technical approach that incorporates all the identified strategies is thus the most robust approach to the threat of viral dissemination of disinformation in the Nigerian political scene.

Recommendations for Mitigating Synthetic Media Threats in Nigeria

Based on the findings of the systematic review, the following targeted recommendations are proposed to build a multi-layered defence against the threats posed by deepfakes and synthetic media in Nigeria.

- The Federal Ministry of Education must mandate the integration of a new, advanced media literacy curriculum into all levels of education. This is a resilience-building strategy and therefore more sustainable. This new curriculum must therefore shift focus from passive analysis to active verification techniques (e.g., SIFT method) and include experiential learning modules to empower individuals to become more critical consumers of information (Naffi et al., 2025).
- The IT Sector and Media should establish a National Content Provenance Standard, which will implement a proactive standard for content authentication, such as cryptographic watermarking or digital signatures. Proactive approaches such as embedding a verifiable watermark or signature into media at the moment of creation is a more resilient strategy.
- The Government should implement, through the National Assembly, legislation that establishes strict civil liability for developers of AI tools primarily designed for malicious deepfake creation and mandates the conspicuous labelling of all AI-generated media.
- Fact-Checking organisations can serve as a Human-AI Rapid Response Hub, an AI verification hub. A hub would allow journalists to use state-of-the-art AI for initial analysis, followed by an expert human.
- Individuals should adopt a “Verify, Then Trust” mindset (mindset of scepticism), which is an active verification of digital content, rather than a passive consumption mindset.

REFERENCES

- Abiodun A. (2024). The impact of fake news and misinformation on political communication and civic engagement in Nigeria. *International Journal of Communication and Public Relation*, 9(1), 26–37. <https://doi.org/10.47604/ijcpr.2272>
- Ahmed, S., Bee, A. W. T., Ng, S. W. T., & Masood, M. (2024). Social media news use amplifies the illusory truth effects of viral deepfakes: A cross-national study of eight countries. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 68(5), 778–805. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08838151.2024.2410783>
- Al Redhaei, A., Fraihat, S., & Al-Betar, M. A. (2025). A self-supervised BEIT model with a novel hierarchical patchReducer for efficient facial deepfake detection. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 58(9), 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-025-10924-4>
- BBC News Pidgin. (2018, November 22). ‘Buhari no be Jubril from Sudan – wetin we know about di conspiracy theory.’ <https://www.bbc.com/pidgin/tori-46263211>
- Centre for Democracy and Development (2023). *Social media and election campaigns: The role of synthetic media and disinformation in Nigeria’s 2023 elections* [Report summary]. CDD West Africa.
- Constantineanu, C. (2024, November 8). *Deepfakes: The new frontier in political disinformation*. The Security Distillery. <https://thesecuritydistillery.org/all-articles/deepfakes-the-new-frontier-in-political-disinformation>.

- Davis E. (2024). *Q&A: Hannah Ajakaiye on manipulated media in the 2023 Nigerian presidential elections, generative AI, and possible interventions*. Institute for Security and Technology. <https://securityandtechnology.org/blog/qa-hannah-ajakaiye/>
- Deressa, D. W., Mareen, H., & Lambert, P. (2025). GenConViT: Deepfake video detection using generative convolutional vision transformer. *Applied Sciences*, 15(12), 6622. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app15126622>
- Ekpang, J. E., Iyorza, S. & Ekpang, P. O. (2023). Social media and artificial intelligence: Perspectives on deepfakes' use in Nigeria's 2023 general elections. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(2), 109–124.
- Fang, S., Zhang, Z., & Song, B. (2025). Deepfake detection model combining texture differences and frequency domain information. *ACM Transactions on Privacy & Security*, 28(2), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1145/>
- Furizal, M. A., Maghfiroh, H., Suwarno, I., Prayogi, D., Kariyamin, L. S., & Sharkawy, A.-N. (2025). Social, legal, and ethical implications of AI-generated deepfake pornography on digital platforms: A systematic literature review. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 12, 101882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101882>
- Heidari, A., Navimipour, N. J., Dag, H., & Unal, M. (2024). Deepfake detection using deep learning methods: A systematic and comprehensive review. *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 14(2), e1520. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1520>
- Igben H. G. O. & Acchugbue O. E. (2024) Influence of Viral Contents on the Rapid Spread of Information on the Social Media Platforms in Nigeria. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 12(6) 24-40. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bjms.2013/vol12n62440>
- Kaddar, B., Fezza, S. A., & Akhtar, Z. (2024). Deepfake detection using spatiotemporal transformer. *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications & Applications*, 20(11), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1145/>
- Karpinska-Krakowiak, M., & Eisend, M. (2025). Realistic portrayals of untrue information: The effects of deepfaked ads and different types of disclosures. *Journal of Advertising*, 54(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2024.2306415>
- Liu, J., Wang, L., Wang, R., Li, H., Yang, Z., Xu, S., & Li, B. (2025). Exposing the forgery clues of DeepFakes via exploring the inconsistent expression cues. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 1, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1002/int>
- Lu, H., & Yuan, S. (2024). “I know it’s a deepfake”: The role of AI disclaimers and comprehension in the processing of deepfake parodies. *Journal of Communication*, 74(5), 359–373. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jqae026>
- Mai, K. T., Bray S., Davies T., & Griffin L. D. (2023) Warning: Humans cannot reliably detect speech deepfakes. *PLoS ONE*, 18(8), e0285333. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0285333>
- Malinka, K., Firc, A., Šalko, M., Prudký, D., Radačovská, K., & Hanáček, P. (2024). Comprehensive multiparametric analysis of human deepfake speech recognition. *Journal of Image Video Processing*, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13640-024-00641-4>
- Matli, W. (2024). Extending the theory of information poverty to deepfake technology. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 4(2), 100286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjime.2024.100286>
- Nadimpalli, A. V., & Rattani, A. (2024). Social media authentication and combating deepfakes using semi-fragile invisible image watermarking. *Digital Threats: Research and Practice*, 5(4), Article 40. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3700146>
- Naffi, N., Charest, M., Danis, S., Bergeron, V., Guertin, J.-S., Paul, R., St-Germain, T., & Savoli, A. (2025). Empowering youth to combat malicious deepfakes and disinformation: An experiential and reflective learning experience informed by personal construct theory. *Journal of Constructivist Psychology*, 38(1), 119–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/>

- Neo, C., Goh, D. H.-L., Rachel, C. W. Y., & Sian Lee, C. (2025). Uncovering strategies for identifying deepfakes. *Information Research*, 30(Conf47209), 752–760. <https://doi.org/10.47989/ir30iConf47209>
- Olley, W. O., & Eloke, O. F. (2021). Public perception of political disinformation and trust in mainstream media during electoral campaigns in Nigeria. *The International Journal of African Language and Media Studies (IJALMS)*, 4(2) 161–175. <https://www.rhyckerex.org/upload/161%20Public%20Perception%20of%20Political%20Disinformation.pdf>
- Owojecho, G. A. (2021). Social media and fake news in Nigeria: A speech act analysis of WhatsApp messages on coronavirus. *Studies in Pragmatics and Discourse Analysis*, 2(1), 56–66. <https://doi.org/10.48185/spda.v2i1.76>
- Oyedeji, O. (2024). Challenges faced by Nigerian fact-checkers with deep fakes during the 2023 general election. *International Journal of Advanced Mass Communication and Journalism*, 5(2), 15–20. <https://doi.org/10.22271/27084450.2024.v5.i2a.81>
- Ramanaharan, R., Guruge, D. B., & Agbinya, J. I. (2025). DeepFake video detection: Insights into model generalisation—A systematic review. *Data and Information Management*, 9(4), Article 100099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dim.2025.100099>
- Ranieri, A. J. (2025). In Too Deep: Navigating an Unpredictable Algorithm. *Touro Law Review* 40(3), 815–849. <https://research.ebsco.com/c/sqzvdv/viewer/pdf/wkjljaeiv>
- Robertson, R., & Meintjes, C. (2021). Towards an Online Risk Mitigation Framework for Political Brands Subject to Computational Propaganda. *Communication*, 47(1), 95–121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02500167.2021.1884578>
- Rosca, C.-M., & Stancu, A. (2025). AI anomaly-based deepfake detection using customized Mahalanobis distance and head pose with facial landmarks. *Applied Sciences*, 15(17), 9574. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app15179574>
- Salihu A. (2020) Fake News as Threat to Democracy in Nigeria. *FUDMA Journal of Politics and International Affairs*, 3(2) 97-107. https://www.academia.edu/77504537/Fake_News_as_Threat_to_Democracy_in_Nigeria.
- Sanchez-Acedo, A., Carbonell-Alcocer, A., Gertrudix, M., & Garcia-Garcia, F. (2024). The challenges of media and information literacy in the artificial intelligence ecology: deepfakes and misinformation. *Communication & Society*, 37(4), 223–239. <https://doi.org/10.1387/cs>
- Sharma, V. K., Garg, R., & Caudron, Q. (2025). A systematic literature review on deepfake detection techniques. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 84(20), 22187-22229.
- Sherman J. (2025). A feast of fraud: how international hesitations to regulate deepfakes are creating a buffet for financial criminals. *The Geo. Wash. Int'l L. Rev.*, 56, 91-117. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/677588e499b0271a0f086536/t/67b788411147e06d465c3e07/1740081217243/Sherman.pdf>
- Shuni, M. A., & Mukoshy, J. I. (2024). Mitigating the effects of social media technologies on Nigeria's elections for sustainable national security. *Middle East Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(3). <https://doi.org/10.36348/merjhss.2024.v04i03.006>
- Somoray, K., Miller, D. J., & Holmes, M. (2025). Human performance in deepfake detection: a systematic review. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies*, 1, 1833228. <https://doi.org/10.1155/hbe2/1833228>
- Uwalaka, T., Amadi, F., & Enyindah, S. (2025). Social media influencers and political influence operations: The data boys example in Nigeria. *Public Relations Inquiry*, 14(1), 89–115. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2046147X241301524>
- Wodajo, D., & Atnafu, S. (2021). *Deepfake video detection using convolutional vision transformer*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2102.11126>

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

- Yao, R., Bai, Z., & Tong, J. (2025). Deepfake detection in image sequences: A temporal approach for anomaly detection. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems, 1*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/int>
- Zeeshan, N., Bakyt, M., Moradpoor, N., & La Spada, L. (2025). Continuous authentication in resource-constrained devices via biometric and environmental fusion. *Sensors, 25*(18), 5711. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25185711>
- Zhang, R., Deng, B., & Cheng, X. (2025). GCS-YOLOV8: A Lightweight Face Extractor to Assist Deepfake Detection. *Sensors, 24*(21), 6781. https://doi.org/10.3390/s24216781__

*The authors extend their appreciation to the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund), Nigeria, for funding this research through the National Research Fund (NRF) under grant number **TETF/DR&D/CE/NRF/2023/UNI/FUTA/HSS/CDS/00061***